

ELECTROCARDIOGRAPHIC MARKERS OF PROARRHYTHMOGENICITY IN METABOLIC SYNDROME

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ЕЛЕКТРОКАРДИОГРАФСКИ МАРКЕРИ ЗА ПРОАРИТМОГЕННОСТ ПРИ МЕТАБОЛИТЕН СИНДРОМ

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Abstract.

The etiopathogenetic mechanisms of metabolic syndrome that affect cardiac electrophysiology and lead to myocardial remodelling are numerous. Cardiomyocyte changes induced by metabolic and proinflammatory factors impair repolarization, exacerbate the heterogeneity of the transmural dispersion of repolarization, and prolong the Tpeak-end interval. Tpeak-Tend interval has been described as a marker of arrhythmogenicity that is more sensitive than the standard QT interval. Multiple pathological conditions and their effect on myocardial repolarisation have been studied – coronary artery disease, sleep apnea, arterial hypertension, Brugada syndrome and other channelopathies, systemic sclerosis, endocrinological diseases such as hypothyroidism, diabetes mellitus, acromegaly, hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, sudden cardiac death, familial hypercholesterolemia, etc. Currently, the most widely accepted theory of the mechanism of formation of Tp-e the interval and its dynamics are transmural myocardial heterogeneity/dispersion repolarisation. For the clinician, this is an additional tool for assessment of arrhythmogenicity through easy and accessible electrocardiographic markers in daily clinical practice. There is very little literature data on the clinical application of electrocardiographic markers (Tp-e interval, Tp-e/QT ratio) for proarrhythmogenicity in patients with metabolic syndrome. Despite progress in the development of new cardiovascular diagnostic methods, electrocardiographic markers can help in daily clinical practice to add important prognostic information about proarrhythmogenicity.

Key words:

metabolic syndrome, electrocardiographic markers, Tp-e interval, Tp-e/QT, cytokines, adiponectin/leptin, interleukin-6, tumor necrosis factor- α

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Резюме.

Етиопатогенетичните механизми на метаболитния синдром, които засягат сърдечната електрофизиология и водят до миокардно ремоделиране, са многобройни. Промените в кардиомиоцитите, предизвикани от метаболитни и провъзпалителни фактори, нарушават реполяризацията, изострят хетерогенността на трансмуралната дисперсия на реполяризацията и удължават интервала Tpeak-end. Интервалът Tpeak-Tend е описан като маркер за аритмогенност, който е по-чувствителен от стандартния QT-интервал. Множество патологични състояния и техният ефект върху реполяризацията на миокарда са изследвани до момента – коронарна артериална болест, сънна апнея, артериална хипертония, синдром на Brugada и други каналопатии, системна склероза, ендокринологични заболявания като хипотиреоидизъм, захарен диабет, акромегалия, хипертрофична кардиомиопатия, внезапна сърдечна смърт, фамилна хиперхолестеролемия и др. В момента най-широко възприетата теория за механизма на образуване на Tp-e интервала и неговата динамика са трансмуралната миокардна хетерогенност/дисперсионна реполяризация. За клинициста електрокардиографските интервали са допълнителен инструмент за оценка на аритмогенността чрез лесни и достъпни електрокардиографски маркери в ежедневно клинична практика. Има много малко литературни данни за клиничното приложение на електрокардиографски маркери (Tp-e интервал, Tp-e/QT съотношение) за проаритмогенност при пациенти с метаболитен синдром. Въпреки напредъка в разработването на нови сърдечно-съдови диагностични методи електрокардиографските маркери могат да помогнат в ежедневно клинична практика да добавят важна прогностична информация за проаритмогенността.

Ключови думи: метаболитен синдром, електрокардиографски маркери, Тр-е интервал, Тр-е/QT, цитокини, адипонектин/лептин, интерлевкин-6, тумор-некротичен фактор- α

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INTRODUCTION

Metabolic syndrome (MS) is one of the most significant diseases, its prevalence increasing yearly. [1] It is a combination of cardiovascular risk factors, including abdominal obesity, hyperglycemia, hypertension, and hypertriglyceridemia. The presence of three or more of these factors increases the levels of circulating proinflammatory cytokines [1, 2].

Risk factors for cardiovascular disease in people with MS are numerous and are characterised by etiopathogenetic mechanisms that contribute to the development of several cardiac nosologies, including arrhythmias, which are less widely recognised in daily clinical practice. Adults with metabolic syndrome are 33% more likely to develop ventricular ectopy, and for every 1 kg/m² increase in body mass index (BMI), the risk of exercise-induced ventricular arrhythmias increases by 4% [3]. According to some studies, MS is an independent risk factor for sudden cardiac death (SCD), regardless of gender and ethnicity [4].

Cardiac arrest in emergency departments is usually due to heart rhythm disturbance – ventricular fibrillation or ventricular tachycardia. The underlying mechanisms are multifactorial. The heterogeneous ventricular activation is most often due to cardiac fibrosis, a consequence of tissue damage.

MECHANISMS OF ARRHYTHMOGENICITY IN METABOLIC SYNDROME

The etiopathogenetic mechanisms in MS that affect cardiac electrophysiology and lead to myocardial remodeling are numerous. The role of arterial hypertension [5], coronary artery disease [6], sleep apnoea [7], diabetes mellitus [8] are some of the most commonly studied factors for risk stratification and therapy. In the current notion of the MS pathogenesis, the MS is considered an inflammatory disease [9, 10]. The COVID-19 pandemic has proven that an acute increase in proinflammatory cytokine levels is an independent risk factor for cardiac arrhythmias, independent of hypoxia and direct myocardial involvement [11]. Metabolic changes at the cardiomyocyte level have attracted the interest of researchers for years. According to modern concepts of the metabolic syndrome trigger, adipocyte dysfunction is generally accepted [12]. The main functions of adipose tissue include reservoir, thermoregula-

tory, mechanical protection of internal organs and endocrine ones. In a balanced calorie intake, adipocytes are characterised by an anabolic mode of functioning leading to the accumulation of fats and carbohydrates in the form of triacylglycerols (TAG). The adipose tissue depots regulation is carried out by several molecules, the following being of particular importance:

1. Adiponectin – a pleiotropic hormone with metabolic, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. The secretion of adiponectin follows a circadian rhythm with the highest levels during the day [13]. Factors promoting the secretion of adiponectin are active lifestyle, weight loss. Medications that increase adiponectin levels are Thiazolidinediones, GLP-1 analogues, antioxidants. Factors that suppress adiponectin secretion are leptin, IL-6 and TNF- α [13]. The metabolic effects of adiponectin are related to sensitising target organs to the effects of insulin by stimulating insulin secretion, GLUT4 expression, and suppressing gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis [13]. Regarding lipid metabolism, adiponectin redirects free fatty acids from visceral to subcutaneous adipose tissue, thereby enhancing insulin sensitivity. It suppresses de novo lipogenesis in the liver. It stimulates the uptake and oxidation of fatty acids in muscles and TAG accumulation in adipocytes [13]. The net metabolic effect of adiponectin secretion is the utilisation of a portion of exogenously absorbed fats and carbohydrates for energy production and the redirection of the rest to adipose tissue depots, while preserving glycogen levels.

2. Leptin – a peptide hormone secreted mainly by adipocytes; its main function is to maintain normal levels of adipose tissue depots. Leptin effects are both auto/ paracrine and endocrine – it promotes lipolysis and beta oxidation of fatty acids; it has a direct effect on the CNS by suppressing hunger; it inhibits the secretion of insulin and glucagon but has an effect on peripheral organs independent of insulin by increasing the influx of glucose to them by mechanisms different from those of insulin [14]. Leptin secretion is pulsatile in nature, with plasma levels following the circadian rhythm of the body – the highest levels are observed in the early morning hours, and the lowest in the afternoon [19]. Food intake also regulates leptin secretion. Not acute, but prolonged hyperinsulinemia stimulates leptin secretion. Corticosteroids and proinflammatory cytokines (IL-6 and TNF- α) stimulate leptin secretion. Catecholamines, through their β 2 and 3 receptors, sup-

press leptin secretion. The effect of leptin stimulation in a catabolic regime is to suppress the deposition and to involve the body's adipose tissue depots in energy production after carbohydrate reserves have already been used. [14] Elevated leptin levels in the context of caloric excess are themselves a sign of adipocyte oversaturation and compensatory insulin resistance aimed at limiting it at the adipocyte level.

Leptin and adiponectin play a major role in controlling the main reservoir function of adipocytes. In a state of caloric excess, respectively metabolic adipocyte distress, local tissue inflammation is activated, aiming to relieve the burden on adipose tissue depots through increased secretion of leptin and reduced secretion of adiponectin [15]. The inhibition of the adipocyte response to the needs of the body and the inability to regulate adipose tissue depots is the basis of the so-called adipocyte dysfunction. Independent examination of the levels of leptin and adiponectin is not sufficient to determine the presence of adipocyte dysfunction. An adiponectin: leptin ratio has been established, its limit being > 1 . Values of < 1 are considered a sign of adipocyte dysfunction.

When the body receives a catabolic stimulus, adipocytes change their mode of operation:

1. Decreased insulin levels suppress TAG synthesis and promote lipolysis.

2. Under the influence of circulating catecholamines and increased sympathetic tone, beta adrenergic receptors are stimulated with subsequent formation of cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP), which, on the one hand, stimulates lipolysis, and on the other hand, the production of IL-6 [16]. IL-6 is pleiotropic cytokine, its effects depending on the provoking stimulus and the cells that synthesise and secrete it [16]. There are two signalling pathways through which IL-6 can exert its effects: the classical pathway, which is stimulated by cAMP, and the nonclassical pathway, which is stimulated by proinflammatory pathways [16, 17]. In the classical pathway, IL-6 must bind not only to its membrane-located receptor (IL-6RA), but also to with membrane IL-6 signal transducer (IL-6ST). For nonclassical stimulation, IL-6 must first bind to the soluble form of IL-6RA and then to IL-6ST. In a proinflammatory state, parallel synthesis of metalloproteases is observed, which release membrane IL-6RA and potentiate its prior binding to IL-6 [18]. The final effects of the classical pathway are anti-inflammatory; they suppress insulin resistance and stimulate leptin secretion. In the nonclassical pathway, a proinflammatory effect is observed with accumulation of leukocytes in adipose tissue, enhanced synthesis of proinflammatory cytokines and insulin resistance at the adipocyte level [16, 17].

Under physiological conditions, i.e. catabolic stimuli, activation of the classical pathway is observed,

promoting lipolysis, suppressing appetite, and maintaining normal caloric balance. The presence of caloric excess, which is the basis of obesity, leads to the overload of adipocytes with lipids and carbohydrates which induce metabolic stress [17, 18]. The excessive influx of fatty acids and their storage in the form of triacylglycerol droplets, combined with excessive protein synthesis, overloads the endoplasmic reticulum of the adipocyte. In a state of endoplasmic reticulum stress, an autoregulatory mechanism called unfolded protein response (UPR) is activated [19-22]. The latter aims to preserve cellular integrity by blocking the import, synthesis and export of molecules and activating mitogenic pathways for cellular hypertrophy. Due to incompletely understood genetic and epigenetic factors, adipocytes subjected to metabolic stress can respond in several ways – with hyperplasia, hypertrophy or both [22]. In hyperplasia, an increase in the number of cells is observed and their normal functioning is preserved. The hyperplastic type of obesity is characterised by a normal glycaemic profile. In adipocyte hypertrophy, an increase in cell volume is observed (> 800 pL according to literature data), which correlates with insulin resistance [22]. In a state of hypertrophic adaptation two mitogenic pathways are stimulated: p38MAPK and JNK. The p38MAPK pathway is characterised by the regulation of cell hypertrophy and induces the synthesis of proinflammatory cytokines [21] and the JNK pathway, which induces insulin resistance at the adipocyte level by reducing the expression of insulin receptors on the cell surface and enhances phosphorylation of those already present [20]. The UPR-activated signalling cascade stimulates the proinflammatory pathway nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B), leading to:

1. IL-6 synthesis and secretion, which has a chemotactic effect on monocytes and macrophages (MF) by increasing their accumulation in adipose tissue [17].

2. Metalloproteases ADAM 10 and ADAM 17 synthesis and secretion, which convert the membrane form of TNF- α into a soluble form, respectively enhance the accumulation of MF in adipose tissue. ADAM 10 and ADAM 17 have a parallel effect on IL-6RA by releasing it from the cell surface and increasing its soluble form [19].

Under physiological conditions, i.e. catabolic stimuli, there is increased production and secretion of IL-6 and low levels of soluble IL-6RA. Stimulation of macrophages via the classical IL-6 signaling pathway is evident, which increases the number of IL-4 receptors and ultimately has an anti-inflammatory effect on MF in adipose tissue [16]. Under pathological conditions, such as caloric excess and inflammatory stimuli for IL-6 production, the parallel synthesis of ADAM10 and ADAM17 increases the amount of soluble IL-6RA, which leads to stimulation of MF via the non-classical signaling pathway, thus inducing a proinflammatory re-

sponse by MF with increased production of proinflammatory cytokines. Cytokines (IL-6 and TNF- α), which maintain the inflammatory process in adipose tissue and increase their plasma levels, lead to endocrine effects on other organs and systems [16, 17].

Cardiomyocytes were found to express receptors for IL-6 and TNF- α . The effects of these receptors are direct (membrane) and indirect (gene). IL-6 enhances the activity of I_{CaL} channels and reduces the expression and activity of I_{Kr} and I_{Ks}. It enhances the expression of RyR, CAMKII and reduces that of SERCA2a and PLB. TNF- α reduces the expression of I_{to}, I_{Kur} and decreases the activity of I_{Kr} and I_{Ks}. An effect on connexin 43 was also observed, where IL-6 induces connexin lateralisation, which slows the rate of impulse propagation through myocardial tissue [23]. The remodeling effect of proinflammatory cytokines encompasses every phase of the myocyte action potential, with the net effect being a repolarisation delay and prolongation, which potentiates arrhythmogenesis. Functional disturbances in the excitation of cardiac tissue may be sufficient to generate arrhythmias, even in the absence of cardiac damage [24, 25]. Uneven disruption of intracellular ion homeostasis and calcium accumulation may disrupt spatially concordant alternans of the myocardium and lead to heterogeneous activation of individual zones and, respectively, discordance in alternans of the action potential and induction of unidirectional conduction block, which is a re-entrant substrate [26].

There is not much data in the literature about the basic mechanisms underlying arrhythmogenic effects of proinflammatory cytokines and their translational affect in the clinical setting. According to the work of Lazzarini et al. inflammatory activation is increasingly recognized as a nonconventional risk factor for arrhythmias, and experimental studies provided robust evidence that this association is mediated by direct arrhythmogenic effects of proinflammatory cytokines (tumor necrosis factor- α – TNF- α ; interleukin-1 – IL-1; IL-6; IL-17) on cardiac cells. Additionally, inflammatory cytokines can favour arrhythmias indirectly through multiple systemic effects. Accumulating data confirm the clinical relevance of these mechanisms; the largest evidence being available for atrial fibrillation, acquired long-QT syndrome, and ventricular arrhythmias [24].

Out of the immunomodulatory cytokines such as interleukin (IL)-6, leading to a state of chronic inflammation in patients over the last decade, increasing evidence has been found to support IL-6 signaling as a powerful predictor of the severity of increased risk for ventricular arrhythmias. IL-6's pro-inflammatory effects are mediated via trans-signaling and may represent a novel arrhythmogenic risk factor in obese hearts [25].

Wang et al. described in a study done amongst Chinese population that high hsCRP, only when combined with metabolic syndrome, had a prognostic value on atrial fibrillation [26].

DIFFERENT ARRHYTHMOGENICITY OF THE ATRIA AND VENTRICLES

When comparing the electrophysiological features of the atria and ventricles, the following significant differences stand out:

1. The action potential (AP) in the atria is different from that in the ventricles. The atria AP is characterised by a lower amplitude and shorter duration than that in the ventricles. The differences are due to different expression of certain ion channels. I_{Kur} and I_{ach} are more pronounced in atrial myocytes than in ventricular ones, accelerating repolarisation and shortening the refractory period. There are interatrial differences in myocyte activity – the ones in the right atrium have a significantly longer AP than those in the left, with cells located around the pulmonary veins characterised by the shortest repolarisation and refractoriness. Factors compromising repolarisation and maintenance of a higher cell membrane potential reduce the number of ready I_{NA}, and respectively myocyte depolarisation. AP at the ventricular level is characterised by heterogeneity among the three layers of the ventricular myocardium – subepicardial, midmyocardial and subendocardial. In the middle layer islands of M cells are located focally. These cells are characterised by a longer AP than the rest of the myocytes and have the ability to further prolong it under the influence of factors inhibiting repolarisation. M cells are characterised by a greater number of late I_{NA}s and a smaller number of I_{Ks}. [27-29].

2. Anisotropy is a vector dependence on the conduction velocity (CV) of the action potential. [30] Anisotropy plays a physiological role in the rapid and synchronous activation and contraction of the cardiac chambers. In certain pathophysiological conditions, anisotropy can induce unidirectional conduction block, re-entry, and potentiate the stabilisation of the re-entry circuit. The impulse conduction in the myocardium is faster longitudinally to the cell, to the muscle fibre than transversely. Anisotropy quantitative characterisation of a given tissue is made by the difference between the highest and lowest CV known as the anisotropic ratio (AR_{CV}) [30]. Atrium AR_{CV} is significantly greater than that of the ventricles, 10 and 2.5-4, respectively, indicating the greater susceptibility of the atrial myocardium to the generation of arrhythmias [30].

The remodeling effect of the proinflammatory cytokines IL-6 and TNF- α potentiates arrhythmogenesis by delaying depolarisation and prolonging repolarisation and the refractory period. From a functional point

of view, the elements of a wave of excitation are the wavefront (zone of depolarisation) and the wave back (zone of repolarisation and refractoriness). When the wavefront of one wave reaches and overlaps with the wave back of a previous wave in that area of the tissue, a wave break forms – a zone of missing excitation. Wave break can occur only in those areas where the conducting impulse is insufficient to induce excitation in the conducted tissue – source-sink-mismatch. This is observed with incompletely restored excitability, i.e. still persistent refractoriness. The myocardium around the wave break zone has preserved conduction and can go around it, thus inducing a re-entry circuit [31]. Adding anisotropy to the altered myocardium electrical activity further increases arrhythmogenesis. The heterogeneous slowing of AP_{CV} along the myocardium, combined with prolonged refractoriness, predisposes to wave break formation and induction of functional re-entry, which are the causes for paroxysmal tachycardias. The significantly higher AR_{CV} of the atrial myocardium predisposes the atria to easier generation and conduction of arrhythmias. The direct stimulation of fibroblasts and the secretion of collagen in the extracellular space are secondary in the beginning, but of importance in more prolonged conditions, and they contribute to the myocardial excitation heterogenization [30, 32, 33]. The accumulation of connective tissue further enhances myocardial anisotropy and potentiates the persistence of re-entry circuits. A factor that stabilises a re-entry circuit is the wavelength, which must be equal to or shorter than the length of the circuit. The wavelength is determined by the product of the average conduction velocity of the impulse and the maximum refractory period of the re-entry circuit [34].

Alterations in cardiomyocyte activity can be detected by ECG, with ventricular activity having a significantly greater amplitude than atrial activity. Therefore, ventricular myocardium remodeling, and especially that of M cells, and prolongation of their activity, has been described to alter T wave morphology by lengthening the T peak–T end interval [35-37].

Informativeness of ECG markers for proarrhythmogenicity

Despite the progress of our knowledge and the many modern imaging methods, the electrocardiogram has been and continues to be considered one of the main screening methods that can provide useful information for assessing arrhythmogenicity in different types of patients. Two groups of SCD markers are known in the literature – depolarisation and repolarisation [38] (Table 1).

Table 1. ECG markers for sudden cardiac death

Depolarization abnormalities	Repolarization abnormalities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • QRS Fragmentation • Q Waves • Prolonged QRS duration • Left posterior fascicular block • Low QRS voltage • Left ventricular hypertrophy • Signal-averaged ECG with late potential • Epsilon wave • Brugada syndrome model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early repolarisation pattern • Tpeak-Tend interval • T-wave alternans • QT interval (long and short) • QT dispersion

Metabolic syndrome is characterised mainly by repolarization abnormalities, but depolarization abnormalities can also be seen. This is associated with the described pathophysiological metabolic and inflammatory changes in MS. Logically, it has not been possible to identify a single electrocardiographic marker that can satisfactorily stratify proarrhythmogenic burden. Over the years, several electrocardiographic markers have been identified that are certainly useful for the overall assessment of proarrhythmic burden [38]. Such electrocardiographic markers include:

T wave alternans

T wave alternans (T_{wa}) is a macroscopic beat-to-beat variation of the T wave in the same lead. The variability may be in the polarity, shape and morphology of the ST-T wave level. It is also described as micro- T_{wa} , which detects Twa signals with a size of up to one millionth of a volt. T_{wa} can be common and is not a pathological finding in cases of elevated heart rate. It is always pathological in cases of heart rate of < 110 beats per minute. The limitation of this parameter is that it is considered useful only in patients with a narrow QRS (< 120 ms) complex. The presence of T_{wa} is due to repolarisation dispersion because of changes in calcium management cycle and its interaction with the late potassium current. A change in AP may predispose to the development of ventricular arrhythmias. A study presented the usefulness of T_{wa} in predicting arrhythmic events in patients with heart failure. Another trial in the same population demonstrated that there is a strong correlation between T_{wa} and SCD in primary prevention. There is no data in the literature for T_{wa} in metabolic syndrome [38].

QT dispersion

QT dispersion is defined as the maximum-minimum QT interval of a 12-lead electrocardiogram. The normal range for QT dispersion is 40-50 ms with a maximum of 65 ms. QT dispersion values above 65 ms identify a high risk of ventricular arrhythmias and SCD. Only highly abnormal values (> 100 ms) may potentially have practical value, reflecting abnormal re-

polarisation. Increased QT dispersion reflects different timing in ventricular AP across the myocardial wall and may be a marker of SCD risk mainly due to predisposition to Torsades de Pointes ventricular tachycardia. QT dispersion as a marker of altered AP propagation has been implicated in the pathogenesis of ventricular arrhythmias in various conditions such as Brugada syndrome, long QT syndrome, short QT syndrome, catecholaminergic paroxysmal ventricular arrhythmia, probably due to early post-depolarisation re-entry into phase 2 and subsequent triggered activity. In patients with hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, QT interval dispersion (cut-off value of 93 ms) has been shown to be associated with an increased SCD risk. There is limited evidence on the proarrhythmic burden of QT dispersion in patients with MS [38].

Tpeak -to-Tend interval

Tpeak -to-Tend interval (Tp-e) has been identified as a marker of arrhythmogenic burden that is more sensitive than the standard QT interval [39, 40]. Multiple pathological conditions and their effect on myocardial repolarisation have been studied in coronary artery disease [6], sleep apnoea [7], arterial hypertension [5], Brugada syndrome and other channelopathies, systemic sclerosis, endocrinological diseases such as hypothyroidism, diabetes mellitus [8], acromegaly, hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, SCD, familial hypercholesterolemia, etc. Currently, the most widely accepted theory of the mechanism of formation of Tp-e the interval and its dynamics are transmural myocardial heterogeneity/myocardial repolarisation dispersion [41]. According to the repolarisation rate the myocardium is divided into three parts – subendocardial, midmyocardial and subepicardial. In the cellular populations first described by Serge Sicouri and Charles Antzelevitch in canine hearts [42] and subsequently in human myocardium by Drouin et al. [43], M cells are located in the midmyocardium. They are characterised by a longer AP and a

tendency towards its further prolongation. Namely the delayed repolarisation of M-cells is considered to be the cause of the formation of the descending limb of the T wave, which forms the Tp-e interval. The peak correlates with the end of repolarisation of the subendocardial and subepicardial cells, and the end – with the middle myocardium. Electrophysiologically, M cells are a hybrid between Purkinje cells and contractile cardiomyocytes [42-43] (Fig. 1).

The Tp-e interval measurement, the interval from the peak of the T wave to the end of the T wave, is related to repolarisation dispersion in the three layers of the cardiac wall, and therefore a prolongation of this interval may suggest the occurrence of ventricular arrhythmias, possibly due to a phase 2 re-entry mechanism. On a standard electrocardiogram, the Tp-e interval is usually measured in the precordial leads. Currently, the normal value in men is 94 ms and in women it is 92 ms. Although it has not been fully validated in all patient subpopulations, there is a general consensus that an interval greater than 100 ms is pathological. Some studies in the general population and in patients with cardiovascular disease are equivocal. There is much evidence for the validity of the Tp-e interval and arrhythmic burden over the years [38].

In 2007, in a population of patients with congenital or acquired prolonged QT interval, it was demonstrated that the Tp-e interval was the best single discriminator of the risk of Torsade de Pointe with a Tp-e interval longer than 117 ms [44]. Similarly, in patients with ST-elevation myocardial infarction, undergoing primary percutaneous coronary intervention, a Tp-e interval greater than 100 ms before primary percutaneous coronary intervention is associated with increased mortality [45]. In patients with left ventricular dysfunction and a left ventricular ejection fraction $\leq 35\%$ who had an implantable cardioverter defibrillator in primary prevention, a Tp-e with a mean value of 107 ms is associated

Fig. 1. Electrocardiographic waves, complexes and intervals

with an increased risk of ventricular tachycardia/ventricular fibrillation and mortality [46].

Tp-e is heart rate dependent, and there is considerable interindividual variability in measurements [38]. Therefore, over the years, it has been suggested that Tp-e be normalised by dividing it by the QT interval measure as an expression of AP duration to improve the predictive value of the Tp-e interval itself with respect to SVC. The optimal ratio is estimated to be between 0.17 and 0.23. In patients with Brugada syndrome undergoing electrophysiological testing, a high Tp-e/QT ratio is associated with induction of ventricular tachycardia/ventricular fibrillation [47]. Similar results were observed in patients with ST-elevation myocardial infarction undergoing primary percutaneous coronary intervention, in whom a Tp-e/QT ratio ≥ 0.29 is associated with major adverse cardiovascular events during follow-up [38].

Metabolic and inflammatory markers in metabolic syndrome

There is limited data in the literature on changes in the Tp-e interval, the Tp-e/QT ratio in newly diagnosed MS, which proves their arrhythmogenic potential [48, 49]. Changes in cardiomyocytes, induced by metabolic and proinflammatory factors, impair repolarisation, exacerbate heterogeneity of transmural dispersion of repolarisation and prolong the Tp-e interval. A number of metabolic and proinflammatory biomarkers have been identified in MS, included in the following groups:

1. **Markers of insulin resistance**, including homeostasis model assessment of insulin resistance [HOMA-IR], triglycerides high-density lipoprotein cholesterol ratio (triglycerides/HDL-cholesterol), triglycerides and glucose index (TyG index). According to data by Sun et al. from January 2025 an increase in the TyG index is an independent risk factor for AF. A 24.26 median year follow-up study involving 11,851 participants revealed a U-shaped interaction between the TyG index and atrial fibrillation incidence, with a stronger association observed in women [48]. A vital linear correlation between the TyG index and atrial fibrillation was found in diabetic patients. The TyG index can serve as a biomarker for risk stratification of advanced atrial fibrillation complications in non-diabetic patients. Given the markedly elevated risk of embolism and other complications in patients with atrial fibrillation, it is imperative to prioritise early detection, diagnosis, and treatment [48].

2. **Cytokines and inflammatory markers**, including interleukin 6, tumor necrosis factor- α , high-sensitivity C-reactive protein, complete blood count: white blood cells, platelets, hemoglobin, mean corpuscular volume.

3. **Adipocytokines**, including leptin, adiponectin, adiponectin/leptin ratio. Scarce data is available in the

literature about the proarrhythmogenic value of the adiponectin/leptin ratio. In their study Zhu et al. found that this ratio independently and negatively associated with the low-frequency/high-frequency ratio in patients with new-onset paroxysmal atrial fibrillation [49].

4. **Biochemistry**, including uric acid, alkaline phosphatase, gammaglutamyl transpeptidase, ionised calcium.

5. **Oxidative stress**, including oxidised LDL [9, 10]. In a study done by Sommariva et al. in 2021 r they present oxidised LDL-dependent pathway as new pathogenic trigger in arrhythmogenic cardiomyopathy.

For daily clinical practice, biomarkers have limited application due to their high cost and lack of wider availability [9, 10].

Last year, it was reported that even in children aged 2 to 18 years, the Tp-e interval and Tp-e/QT ratios are more sensitive to the occurrence of ventricular arrhythmias in obese children with insulin resistance than in those without insulin resistance. The authors discussed the need for careful assessment of atrial and ventricular depolarisation and repolarisation parameters with electrocardiography during examinations in obese children with insulin resistance and recommend 24-hour Holter monitoring if necessary to detect arrhythmias [50].

Studies showed a strong association between metabolic syndrome and the development of atrial fibrillation. The left atrium in MS is multifactorially involved, leading to atrial remodeling, thus providing both the substrate and the necessary trigger, which likely plays a key role in the progression of atrial fibrillation. There is less evidence on the association between MS and ventricular arrhythmias.

Atrial fibrillation, obesity, metabolic syndrome

Obesity is a major risk factor for atrial fibrillation, with obese patients being more likely to develop atrial fibrillation than individuals with normal weight. Adipose tissue leads to left atrial enlargement and electrical remodeling through various mechanisms, including inflammation and oxidative stress. This triggers the development of atrial fibrillation and promotes type switching. Weight loss reduces the development of atrial fibrillation and is associated with a reduced incidence of atrial fibrillation recurrence after ablation. Although the relationship between obesity and atrial fibrillation is well established, the pathophysiological mechanisms are complex and not fully understood. For example, from a metabolic perspective, obesity patients are divided into metabolically healthy and metabolically impaired. Even if metabolically healthy obese patients have a high BMI, the risk of atrial fibrillation is low; thus, using BMI alone to identify obesity is not accurate. Waist circumference is a mandatory component

of the metabolic syndrome (men > 94 cm, women > 80 cm), and the height/waist circumference ratio (reference values 2:1) are more accurate parameters for assessing obesity.

There are in-depth analyses in the literature of the types of adipose tissue – white, beige and brown, which are distributed throughout the body and function differently and carry different risks of atrial fibrillation. Obesity is a risk factor for recurrence of paroxysmal atrial fibrillation after catheter ablation, but not for permanent atrial fibrillation. Studies are needed to investigate the differences in the development of paroxysmal and permanent atrial fibrillation. Obesity in early life is a better predictor of atrial fibrillation risk than throughout adulthood. Further studies are required to investigate the mechanisms by which early obesity promotes the development of atrial fibrillation.

Epicardial adipose tissue in obese patients plays a key role in left atrial structural and electrical remodeling. The size and the thickness of the epicardial tissue predicts the occurrence, development and switching of the type of atrial fibrillation. However, current imaging techniques used to detect epicardial adipose tissue cannot meet the requirements of speed, economy, and accuracy at the same time, and cannot quantify the relationship between epicardial adipose tissue volume and atrial fibrillation severity and prognosis. Understanding the role of epicardial adipose tissue in atrial fibrillation is still in the clinical research stage. Studying the possibility of linking epicardial adipose tissue to atrial fibrillation diagnosis and treatment could be an important direction in the future research.

Necessity for easy, accessible and reproducible methods for assessing arrhythmogenicity in metabolic syndrome

In daily clinical practice, we need easy, accessible and reproducible methods for assessing proarrhythmogenicity in metabolic obesity, respectively in metabolic syndrome. The use of markers of inflammation, oxidative stress, assessment of epicardial adipose tissue is not applicable at this stage, because they do not meet the requirements for speed, economy, accuracy and repeatability.

A review of the literature in recent years showed that electrocardiography provides both diagnostic and prognostic information for the assessment of arrhythmogenicity and is therefore a powerful diagnostic tool for the prevention of SCD in many cardiac nosological entities. The need for easy, accessible and reproducible clinical studies in MS leads to the need to verify the available electrocardiographic markers of arrhythmogenicity in the high-risk population of patients with MS, including Tp-e interval, Tp-e/QT ratio in order to

assess the possibility of using them as early and easy markers in daily clinical practice. At this stage, there is limited data on the arrhythmogenicity of the Tp-e interval and Tp-e/QT ratio in patients with MS. The study of this issue in the future will have important practical value in these high-risk patients with newly diagnosed MS for the purpose of diagnosis and treatment of asymptomatic rhythm disorders and prevention of their progression to more severe forms.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, despite the presence of numerous established metabolic and proinflammatory biomarkers in MS, there is very little data on the clinical application of electrocardiographic markers (Tp-e interval, Tp-e/QT ratio) for proarrhythmogenicity in MS patients. For the clinician, this is an additional tool for assessing arrhythmogenicity through easy and accessible electrocardiographic markers in daily clinical practice. Despite the progress in the development of new cardiovascular diagnostic methods, the renaissance of electrocardiographic markers aims to help cardiologists in their daily clinical practice to assess prognostically correct electrocardiographic intervals and indices.

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